

The Impact of Exchange Rate Fluctuations on Brazilian Imports

O Impacto das Flutuações Cambiais nas importações brasileiras
El Impacto de las Fluctuaciones Cambiarias en las Importaciones

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on various sectors of the Brazilian economy, aiming to demonstrate how these variations affected the country's trade balance during the first half of 2024. The research adopts a qualitative, quantitative, and descriptive approach, based on official economic data, and links exchange rate oscillations to specific economic events, such as domestic crises and changes in the dollar's value. The findings show that, during periods of appreciation of the Brazilian real, imports tend to increase, whereas depreciation boosts exports, albeit raising the cost of imported inputs. It is concluded that exchange rate fluctuations represent a significant barrier to Brazilian international trade, requiring effective mitigation strategies and continuous monitoring to maintain competitiveness in the global market.

Keywords: *Exchange rate fluctuation; Brazilian imports; Currency; Economy.*

Resumo:

Este estudo investiga o impacto das flutuações cambiais nos diversos setores da economia brasileira, com o objetivo de demonstrar como essas variações afetaram a balança comercial do país no primeiro semestre de 2024. A pesquisa adota uma abordagem qualitativa, quantitativa e descritiva, baseada em dados econômicos oficiais, e associa as oscilações da taxa de câmbio a eventos econômicos específicos, como crises nacionais e mudanças no valor do dólar. Os resultados indicam que, em períodos de valorização do real, as importações tendem a crescer, enquanto a desvalorização favorece as exportações, embora encareça os insumos importados. Conclui-se que as flutuações cambiais representam uma barreira significativa ao comércio internacional brasileiro, exigindo estratégias eficazes de mitigação e monitoramento contínuo para manter a competitividade no mercado global.

Palavras-chave: Flutuação cambial; Importações brasileiras; Câmbio; Economia.

Resumen:

Este estudio investiga el impacto de las fluctuaciones cambiarias en diversos sectores de la economía brasileña, con el objetivo de demostrar cómo estas variaciones afectaron la balanza comercial del país durante el primer semestre de 2024. La investigación adopta un enfoque cualitativo, cuantitativo y descriptivo, basado en datos económicos oficiales, y relaciona las oscilaciones del tipo de cambio con eventos económicos específicos, como crisis internas y variaciones en el valor del dólar. Los resultados indican que, en períodos de apreciación del real brasileño, las importaciones tienden a aumentar, mientras que la depreciación favorece las exportaciones, aunque encarece los insumos importados. Se concluye que las

fluctuaciones cambiarias representan una barrera significativa para el comercio internacional brasileño, exigiendo estrategias eficaces de mitigación y un monitoreo constante para mantener la competitividad en el mercado global.

Palabras clave: *Fluctuación cambiaria; Importaciones brasileñas; Tipo de cambio; Economía.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the foreign exchange market, exchange rate volatility plays a crucial role in the balance of global trade, accurately reflecting the economic and political actions of nations. This article aims to understand how this important economic variable directly influences various sectors of the economy, affecting foreign trade and, consequently, national economic dynamics.

Given the constantly changing global economic landscape, this study aims to analyze how these changes influence exchange rate fluctuations. To this end, it initially seeks to define the exchange rate and highlight its relevance as a fundamental element in international trade relations.

Exchange rate fluctuations reflect both internal and external factors, including monetary policy, the trade balance, interest rates, and international reserves. It is essential that organizations and managers understand the dynamics of these fluctuations to ensure operational stability in the Brazilian international market.

In the Brazilian context, where the economy is heavily dependent on foreign trade, changes in the exchange rate significantly affect imports. As an emerging country, Brazil is particularly vulnerable to these fluctuations, given its need to import essential inputs and products for various economic sectors.

When the Brazilian real appreciates against foreign currencies, imports become more accessible, increasing external purchasing power. Conversely, the depreciation of the national currency raises the cost of imported products, reducing importers' interest and putting pressure on domestic production.

This scenario represents one of the main challenges faced by the Brazilian economy, given the wide range of imported products, from raw materials to final consumer goods. The impact of exchange rate fluctuations on imports is not isolated; it is interconnected with factors such as inflation, the competitiveness of the national industry, and public policies regulating foreign trade.

Given this context, the present study examines how exchange rate fluctuations pose barriers to international trade, directly affecting importers and exporters. To this end, data from the first half of 2024 will be analyzed to demonstrate how these exchange rate variations affect Brazilian competitiveness in the global context.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 CONCEPT OF FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET AND EXCHANGE RATE FLOAT

The foreign exchange market is a global "virtual environment" for buying and selling foreign currencies, where international financial institutions conduct commercial transactions. The term originated in 1808 with the creation of Banco do Brazil, the first Brazilian bank, established by the royal family shortly after their arrival in Brazil.

The central issue with exchange rates is that they represent the price of one

currency in terms of another in international markets. For example, in Brazil, the value of the real is constantly compared to the dollar, the world's main reference currency.

For many years, Brazil maintained a fixed exchange rate regime, a measure widely used in Latin America, aimed at reducing the prices of imported goods and controlling local inflation. This regime was effective in reducing imports but proved a significant barrier to exports, resulting in large trade deficits, with losses reaching approximately US\$720 million by the end of the period. Faced with these deficits, Brazil became dependent on foreign investment.

With the implementation of the Real Plan in 1994 and the subsequent transition to a floating exchange rate regime in 1999, during the government of Fernando Henrique Cardoso, Brazil adopted a flexible exchange rate system, which remains in effect to this day. The Brazilian foreign exchange market uses the exchange rate model known as "dirty float." This model allows the Central Bank to intervene in the market whenever necessary to control currency fluctuations, but indirectly through monitoring and observation.

Although the term "exchange rate fluctuation" is often associated with uncertainty and unpredictability, it reflects the dynamics of supply and demand. Like any monetary regime, a floating exchange rate has strengths and weaknesses. One of its main benefits is the decentralization of the country's economic focus, allowing Brazil to concentrate on issues that support exchange rate stability without the need for rigid government control of the exchange rate.

Brazil faced turbulent periods until 2003. However, from 2004 to 2011, the real appreciated, driven by growing global demand for commodities. The country experienced a significant increase in exports, with the Brazilian currency reaching R\$1.56 per US\$1.00, the lowest level since the adoption of the floating exchange rate regime, which strengthened the purchasing power of the real, with an effective value of 70%. From 2012 onwards, the real entered a period of depreciation, but with relatively more stable performance than in previous periods.

In summary, Brazil has experienced different exchange rate regimes over time, adopting varied approaches to managing its exchange rate. Exchange rate fluctuations, therefore, reflect both changes in the global financial market and internal decisions related to the country's economic policy.

2.2 EXCHANGE RATE VARIATIONS IN BRAZILIAN IMPORTS: AN ANALYSIS FROM JANUARY TO JULY

This chapter presents data on the Brazilian trade balance from January to July 2024, based on monthly reports from the Ministry of Development, Industry and Foreign Trade (MDIC), with a focus on exchange rate movements and their implications for imports.

The trade balance comprises imports and exports, which represent the international purchases and sales of tangible goods produced by a country's primary and secondary sectors. When exports exceed imports in monetary terms, it results in a trade surplus (Silva, 2019).

Table 1 - Brazilian trade balance from January to July 2024

Mês	Exp Valor US\$ Milhões	Exp Média US\$ Milhões	Imp Valor US\$ Milhões	Imp Média US\$ Milhões
07/2024	30.918,7	1.344,3	23.279,1	1.012,1
06/2024	28.765,8	1.438,3	22.381,4	1.119,1
05/2024	30.201,1	1.438,1	21.875,2	1.041,7
04/2024	30.478,2	1.385,4	21.881,8	994,6
03/2024	27.710,7	1.385,5	20.494,6	1.024,7
02/2024	23.419,2	1.232,6	18.222,5	959,1
01/2024	26.708,4	1.214,0	20.511,8	932,4

Source: Federal Revenue Service (2024)

Table 2 - Average dollar price during the quoted period

Mês	Valor médio de VENDA US\$	Valor médio de COMPRA US\$
07/2024	5,3630	5,3624
06/2024	5,1423	5,1417
05/2024	5,1746	5,1740
04/2024	4,9937	4,9931
03/2024	4,9710	4,9704
02/2024	4,8765	4,8759
01/2024	4,9397	4,9391

Fonte: Receita Federal (2024)

2.2.1 JANUARY

In January, the dollar registered R\$ 4.93. Brazilian exports benefited from the devaluation of the real, which made domestic products more competitive in international markets. However, imports did not grow at the same rate. Agribusiness, still in the off-season for soybeans, reduced the demand for imported inputs, negatively impacting the volume of external purchases in this sector (MDIC, 2024).

2.2.2 FEBRUARY

With the dollar quoted at R\$ 4.87 in February, there was a slight decrease in both imports and exports compared to January. The stability of the exchange rate in relation to the previous month was a key factor. However, trade performance improved, with the first two months of 2024 registering record numbers compared to previous years. In addition, there was an improvement in the agricultural, extractive industry and manufacturing sectors, which were preparing for the following months (MDIC, 2024).

2.2.3 MARCH

In March, the dollar remained stable at R\$ 4.93. However, there was a global drop in soybean and oil prices, and the Holy Week holiday, which coincided with Easter, was rare. The start of the harvest required fewer inputs, such as fertilizers and machinery. Despite the slowdown in March, the quarter recorded record surpluses (MDIC, 2024).

2.2.4 APRIL

April saw increases in both imports and exports, with exports up 5.7% and imports up 2.2%. The first four months of 2024 had a record surplus. The most exported products were, once again, petroleum, and, for the first time, sugar, which compensated for the end of the soybean harvest and the Argentine crisis in the automotive sector. According to the MDIC (Ministry of Development,

Industry and Foreign Trade), the effects of the floods in Rio Grande do Sul only began to impact the figures from May onwards (MDIC, 2024).

2.2.5 MAY

In May, Brazil's trade balance recorded a surplus of US\$8.534 billion, driven by increased exports of oil, soybeans, and iron ore amid rising global demand for these commodities. This increase in exports helped offset the impact of exchange rate fluctuations, as the dollar remained relatively stable compared to the previous month (MDIC, 2024).

2.2.6 JUNE

In June, the dollar surpassed the R\$ 5.17 mark. Imports remained mainly in the agricultural sector, which saw the most growth that month, although exports fell. However, Brazilian exports reached record highs, driven mainly by sales of iron ore, bituminous minerals, and manufactured goods (MDIC, 2024).

2.2.7 JULY

In July, imports recovered, with the dollar stabilizing at R\$5.54. The resumption of major infrastructure projects and preparations for new harvests encouraged an increase in external purchases of machinery and inputs. The stabilization of the exchange rate, along with increased exports, created a more favorable environment for imports, partially reversing the trend toward greater export growth observed in previous months (MDIC, 2024).

As demonstrated in this chapter, Brazil has maintained a steady evolution, rarely registering declines. This stability suggests that, in times of exchange rate stability, economic growth is more predictable and less affected by exchange rate fluctuations, with Brazilian exports remaining on a growth trajectory, and the manufacturing industry playing a key role in imports.

3. METHOD

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative analyses to understand why exchange rate fluctuations act as barriers to international trade. Initially, a documentary analysis was conducted to identify the main variations in the Brazilian trade balance over the period under review.

Academic sources, such as scientific articles, were used, along with specialized, reliable websites that provide up-to-date economic and commercial data. This strategy allowed for a more precise contextualization of the reasons why exchange rate fluctuations represent obstacles to foreign trade.

Data regarding exchange rates and the volume of Brazilian imports were collected from official and specialized sources, covering the period from January to July 2024. This information was organized and subjected to a qualitative analysis, relating exchange rate variations to specific economic events of each month, such as national crises and changes in the value of the dollar.

The methodology also included a descriptive analysis, aimed at identifying

patterns and trends in Brazilian imports in response to exchange rate fluctuations. This approach made it possible to understand how exchange rate changes affect import costs and the volume of foreign purchases, revealing market reactions to fluctuations in the national currency.

The study focuses on the relationship between the exchange rate and Brazilian imports, providing a detailed view of the effects of exchange rate fluctuations on the country's foreign trade. The qualitative analysis contributed to an understanding of market behavior and reinforced the thesis that exchange rate fluctuations pose significant barriers to international trade.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study made it possible to identify the origins of the terms "exchange rate fluctuation" and "foreign exchange market," offering a well-founded historical and conceptual contextualization. The foreign exchange market is a global virtual environment for buying and selling foreign currencies, where financial institutions conduct transactions in international currencies. The term exchange rate, in turn, refers to the value of one currency relative to another in the international market.

The banking history of Brazil dates to 1808, when the Portuguese royal family created the Bank of Brazil. Since then, the country has gone through different exchange rate regimes, with a fixed exchange rate predominant until the mid-1990s, when a floating exchange rate regime was adopted and has remained in effect.

Based on the methods applied, it was possible to ascertain that trade barriers arising from exchange rate fluctuations largely result from strategies adopted by companies to mitigate financial losses. A clear example is the reduction of imports during periods of a strong dollar, aimed at preserving profit margins amid rising costs.

Qualitative and descriptive research allowed for the analysis of the evolution of the exchange rates of the US dollar (US\$) against the Brazilian real (BRL), as presented below:

Figure 1 – Dollar price from January to July 2024

Source: Pacific Exchange Rate Service – University of British Columbia (2024)

Analysis of Figure 1 reveals a significant upward trend in the value of the dollar during the period analyzed. This movement led to noticeable changes in Brazil's trade balance, especially in the months following the exchange rate increases. In this scenario, imports were concentrated in specific sectors of the economy, demonstrating a pattern of selective stability during periods of US dollar appreciation.

It can be argued that exchange rate fluctuations directly impact not the overall growth of the industry, but rather on which specific sectors will thrive or contract. While certain segments experience a decline in the face of a stronger dollar, others gain strength and manage to increase import and export levels, often offsetting deficits in declining areas.

Applying the proposed methodology, it was observed that Brazilian foreign trade generally maintained a trajectory of continuous growth, even amid exchange rate fluctuations. The country rarely experienced significant declines during the period analyzed. In periods of relative exchange rate stability, economic growth proved resilient, though subject to occasional fluctuations in the value of the dollar. In this context, the manufacturing industry stands out as one of the main drivers of export growth, consolidating itself as a central element in the import system.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study on the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on Brazilian imports and exports highlighted the importance of exchange rates for the country's foreign trade. Fluctuations in the exchange rate directly influence the costs and competitiveness of Brazilian products in both international and domestic markets, affecting the volume of goods imported and exported.

During periods of appreciation of the Brazilian real, imports tend to increase, as purchasing power in foreign currency expands. On the other hand, the depreciation of the national currency favors exports, making Brazilian products more competitive abroad, although it increases the cost of imported inputs, which can compromise domestic production. This dynamic reinforces the importance of economic policies that mitigate the effects of exchange rate fluctuations, promoting greater stability for the national productive sector.

Based on the analyses conducted, it is concluded that the exchange rate has a decisive influence on Brazil's foreign trade performance. As demonstrated, exchange rate fluctuations affect companies' profitability and strategies, unevenly impacting sectors—while some suffer setbacks, others benefit and grow. This behavior highlights the volatility of the Brazilian market and the need for constant adaptation amid an unstable international economic environment.

This study aimed to understand how exchange rate fluctuations directly affect various sectors of the Brazilian economy, with an emphasis on their influence on foreign trade. The results confirmed the importance of the exchange rate as a determinant of the competitiveness of Brazilian products in the global market, aligning with the objectives proposed at the beginning of the research.

The data indicate that, in contexts of currency appreciation, imports grow due to increased purchasing power in foreign currency. Conversely, the depreciation of the real benefits of exports increases production costs due to greater dependence on imported inputs. This complexity reinforces the need for attention from companies and the government on exchange rate policies to maintain external competitiveness and a balanced trade balance.

Among the limitations of this study, the restricted access to up-to-date sources and data stands out, hindering a more in-depth and comprehensive analysis. Furthermore, the research focused on the first half of 2024, limiting the generalization of the results to other periods or economic sectors. Exchange rate behavior is influenced by various cyclical factors and can exhibit different dynamics over time.

For future research, it is recommended to expand the analysis to longer periods and include different economic cycles and productive sectors, which will allow for a more robust and detailed understanding of the prolonged effects of exchange rate fluctuations. It is also suggested that comparative studies be conducted between companies that adopt exchange rate mitigation strategies, such as hedging, and those that do not, to identify more effective practices for reducing the negative impacts of exchange rate fluctuations. Finally, it would be pertinent to explore how adjustments to monetary policy can contribute to greater economic stability amid exchange rate volatility.

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